

**MARKETING STRATEGY FOR COCKLE FISH PROCESSING PRODUCTS BASED ON
DIGITAL MARKETING (STUDY ON RAYHANA REZKY FOOD MSME
IN SINJAI REGENCY)**

Naufal Asri

Business and Entrepreneurship Department, Faculty of Economics and Business,
Makassar State University, Indonesia
Correspondensi author email: naufalasri4@gmail.com

Agus Syam

Business and Entrepreneurship Department, Faculty of Economics and Business,
Makassar State University, Indonesia
agus.syam@unm.ac.id

Muhammad Jufri

Business and Entrepreneurship Department, Faculty of Economics and Business,
Makassar State University, Indonesia
muhammad.jufri@unm.ac.id

Muhammad Rakib

Business and Entrepreneurship Department, Faculty of Economics and Business,
Makassar State University, Indonesia
m.rakib@unm.ac.id

Nur Halim

Business and Entrepreneurship Department, Faculty of Economics and Business,
Makassar State University, Indonesia
nur.halim@unm.ac.id

Abstract

This study aims to examine the digital marketing strategies used by Rayhana Rezky Food, a micro, small, and medium enterprise (MSME) engaged in cockle fish processing in Sinjai Regency. In response to the growing importance of digital platforms, this research analyzes how digital tools and online media are utilized to enhance market reach and customer engagement. A qualitative descriptive method was applied, with data collected through interviews, observation, and documentation. The findings indicate that the business actively uses social media platforms such as Instagram and Facebook, as well as messaging apps like WhatsApp, for promotional activities, customer interaction, and product dissemination. These digital marketing strategies have helped improve brand awareness and increase product sales. However, challenges remain, including limited digital skills and infrastructure. The study concludes with suggestions for strengthening digital literacy and optimizing e-commerce platforms to support the long-term sustainability of MSMEs in the seafood processing sector.

Keywords : Marketing Strategy, Digital Marketing, Cockle Fish Processed Products, MSMEs, Rayhana Rezky Food, Sinjai Regency, Small Business Development.

INTRODUCTION

Marketing in the business world today is heading towards competition in the increasingly vast market dominance. This is marked by the numerous businesses competing in product marketing using various methods to sell their products to as many consumers as possible. Marketing is a total system of business activities designed to plan, set prices, promote, and distribute goods or services that can satisfy consumer needs and desires (Aliyah, Z., 2018). Marketing is an effective and strategic process in achieving business objectives. Every business must engage in marketing to expand and dominate the market using mastered marketing strategies to increase product sales (Juandi, M., 2021).

Marketing strategy is the steps of marketing or promoting a product in relation to market opportunities to achieve business objectives (Husriah et al., 2021). In marketing strategy, a business can achieve optimal results by first recognizing its strengths and weaknesses. This greatly helps a business to recognize itself in utilizing every available opportunity and minimizing or avoiding threats. Marketing strategies can determine a favorable marketing position for a business amidst the ongoing competitive conditions. In this increasingly connected era, marketing strategies have undergone a significant paradigm shift. One of the biggest changes in the marketing world is the shift from traditional methods to digital marketing. Digital marketing is a marketing method that is currently being widely used in every business. Digital marketing is a general term for the targeted, measurable, and interactive marketing of goods or services using digital technology (Wati et al., 2020). Undeniably, technology and the internet have permeated every aspect of life, changing the way we interact, shop, and even think. One of the businesses that has implemented this digital marketing system in its operations is IKM Rayhana Rezky Food.

IKM Rayhana Rezky Food is located within the Technical Implementation Unit of the Small and Medium Industry Center (IKM) in Sinjai Regency. The brand of products from IKM Rayhana Rezky Food is called Koki Duyung. IKM Rayhana Rezky Food, in running its business, has implemented marketing by utilizing digital media through social media. However, the digital-based marketing that has been implemented is still not optimal, making it the main obstacle in marketing the processed fish products. In fact, the local product has its own advantages and can compete with other products, both in terms of quality and price. Therefore, a marketing strategy analysis is needed to address the marketing issues of the product.

To determine the marketing strategy, an analysis needs to be conducted. One of the tools for analyzing marketing strategies that can be used is by conducting a Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats (SWOT) analysis.

SWOT analysis includes efforts to identify the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats that drive business performance (Mashuri & Nurjannah, 2020). SWOT analysis is a systematic factor identification tool for formulating company strategies. Therefore, SWOT analysis plays an important role in every policy implemented in running a business. Based on the background that has been outlined, the main issue

lies in the product marketing strategy.

RESEARCH METHOD

In this study, a qualitative approach with a descriptive research type is used. The qualitative approach was chosen because the research focuses on in-depth observation of a phenomenon or problem being studied. On the other hand, the descriptive method was chosen because the researcher aims to elaborate or describe an object being studied in depth, detail, or breadth. Qualitative descriptive research is a research strategy in which the researcher investigates events, phenomena of individuals' lives, and asks one or a group of individuals to narrate their lives. This information is then retold by the researcher in a descriptive chronology (Kusumastuti & Khoirin, 2019). The type of qualitative descriptive research will present the available data as it is, without modification or manipulation, where the purpose of this research is to provide a complete picture of a phenomenon or clarify an ongoing phenomenon.

Therefore, the type of research used by the researcher is the qualitative descriptive method because this research aims to explain or describe an event or phenomenon, namely the Marketing Strategy of Cooked Goldfish Products Based on Digital Marketing (A Study on Rayhana Rezky Food SMEs in Sinjai Regency).

The focus of the research is an element or factor that helps researchers concentrate on the research topic they are working on. This research will focus on the marketing strategy for processed fish products from Koki Duyung based on digital marketing, which is expected to formulate strategies that can address product marketing issues.

The focus description in this research discusses each indicator of marketing and digital marketing strategies, as well as formulating methods using SWOT analysis. The strength of the marketing for the processed fish products from Koki Duyung by IKM Rayhana Rezky Food lies in the quality of the products, but the weakness is the inconsistency in fully utilizing digital marketing. Then, the marketing opportunity for the processed fish products of Koki Duyung from IKM Rayhana Rezky Food can be reached by many social media users, giving it a wide market share for its products. Meanwhile, the threat is the numerous competitors with similar products using digital marketing to promote their products, which could make IKM Rayhana Rezky Food's products less known to the public.

The data analysis in this study is qualitative descriptive, with the analysis conducted during the data collection period and after the data collection period within a certain timeframe. The data analysis activities used include internal and external factor analysis with IFAS and EFAS matrices, SWOT diagram, and SWOT matrix.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This research discussion will elaborate on the marketing strategy of digital marketing-based products as a foundation of information regarding the marketing of processed products from dugong fish using digital marketing applied by IKM Rayhana Rezky Food. After that, conduct a SWOT analysis as a tool for processing the research

data. SWOT analysis is used to determine the most appropriate strategy for IKM Rayhana Rezky Food by examining various aspects of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats.

1. Analysis of Marketing Strategy for Cooked Fish Products by Koki Duyung Based on Digital Marketing Study on IKM Rayhana Rezky Food in Sinjai Regency.

Marketing strategy is an effort to market goods or services carried out in order to achieve specific goals. The marketing strategy implemented by IKM Rayhana Rezky Food is based on considering marketing indicator aspects, namely:

a) Market Selection

In selecting a market, IKM Rayhana Rezky Food first identifies the needs and target market, whether direct consumers or places where the products will be marketed. After that, they proceed with production and also collaborate with several stores and institutions to market the products. This is supported by research findings (Mustaan & Nizar Hamdi, 2021), based on the study of the role of marketing strategies to increase sales volume at the Master Gift Box Malang company. On the market selection indicator, the strategic value of market segmentation is to direct buyers to their products. How the characteristics of consumers identify effective ways to serve each market segment. This shows that the Master Gift Box company meets customer needs, leading to customer loyalty towards Master Gift Box products.

b) Product Planning

IKM Rayhana Rezky Food conducts product planning by directly requesting feedback from consumers or through the results of participating in product competitions, where both methods are evaluated to ensure the product meets market needs. This is supported by research findings (Mustaan & Nizar Hamdi, 2021) on the product planning indicator. The products offered to consumers aim to meet their needs. The product packaging is attractive and in line with trends, the brand is well-known, and the product quality is good and high-quality, which can attract consumer attention and loyal customers to the product.

c) Pricing Determination

IKM Rayhana Rezky Food sets prices based on product quality, so the prices set are slightly higher than competing products, but the prices offered remain affordable for consumers. That statement is in line with the research findings (Mustaan & Nizar Hamdi, 2021) on the pricing indicator. In determining the price, it must be adjusted according to the product demanded by consumers and customers, and consider the quality as well as the price set according to the market segment of the product. Prices that are too high, products that do not meet the respondents' desires, and pricing that does not align with the market segment can reduce sales volume and cause customers to switch to other products.

d) Distribution System

IKM Rayhana Rezky Food, in managing its distribution system, divides the time and location of its production to be efficient and effective, thereby meeting market demand

until the products reach the end consumers. This is in accordance with the research findings (Mustaan & Nizar Hamdi, 2021) on the distribution system indicators. With a good and orderly distribution system, products can reach customers. With strategic marketing locations, consumers and customers can easily obtain products, and the availability of products allows consumers and customers to choose the desired products.

e) Promotion

IKM Rayhana Rezky Food is still lacking in product promotion on social media. Promotion through digital media aims to influence consumer behavior so that they become aware of and are more inclined to choose the promoted products or services. Therefore, promotion through digital marketing becomes a factor that needs to be considered by IKM Rayhana Rezky Food in marketing their products. This is reinforced by the research findings (Mustaan & Nizar Hamdi, 2021) on the promotion indicator. Appropriate and good advertising media can enhance the brand of a product, thereby influencing the sales level. With effective promotion, consumers and customers will recognize and use the product.

Next is digital marketing, which is a marketing method that utilizes technology in every process it undertakes. For IKM Rayhana Rezky Food, this digital marketing concept has been implemented in its product marketing by utilizing social media platforms like Facebook, Instagram, and WhatsApp to promote products and reach potential customers.

2. Internal and External Factors of IKM Rayhana Rezky Food in Sinjai Regency.

The internal strengths (Strength) of IKM Rayhana Rezky Food in Sinjai Regency include: (1) Having updated social media, (2) Attractive product advertisements, (3) Maintaining the legality of marketed products, (4) Advertisement content containing product information, (5) Having consumer interaction data. Then, the internal weaknesses of IKM Rayhana Rezky Food include: (1) Limited promotional social media accounts, (2) Challenges in building product trust, (3) Incomplete product promotion information. The external opportunity conditions for IKM Rayhana Rezky Food are: (1) A wide market share, (2) Direct interaction with consumers, (3) Engaging promotional content that easily goes viral, (4) Strengthening consumer testimonials. Then, the external threat conditions (Threats) include: (1) More aggressive promotions from competitors, (2) Cybercrime in digital marketing.

3. SWOT Diagram

Based on the SWOT analysis diagram in table 6.3, the Strength score is 2.4 and the Weakness score is 1.2. Opportunity score: 2.3 and threat score: 1.2. Therefore, it can be concluded that the strength factor exceeds the existing weaknesses with a score difference of 1.2. Meanwhile, the opportunity factor exceeds the threat factor by a margin of score 1,1. The difference values can form coordinates, namely (1,2;1,1). In the Cartesian diagram, it is known that the SWOT analysis of IKM Rayhana Rezky Food is in quadrant 1. The strategy that should be used in this situation is to support an aggressive strategy. IKM Rayhana Rezky Food has opportunities and strengths, so the strategy in this condition can support an aggressive growth policy, commonly referred to as a Growth Oriented Strategy. This is in line with the research conducted by (Suardika & Yasa, 2022), which states that the

Growth Oriented Strategy is a strategy that maximizes the existing strengths to seize available opportunities, allowing it to compete with other businesses and even win the business competition.

4. SWOT Matrix

The S-O (Strength-Opportunity) strategy is a strategy that utilizes all strengths to seize and maximize opportunities. The SO strategy that can be pursued by IKM Rayhana Rezky Food is to utilize the latest social media to increase interaction with consumers and expand market share, leverage product advertisement content that includes information about the legality of the product that is engaging and easily goes viral, and utilize interaction data to strengthen consumer testimonials. This strategy aims to leverage social media to gather consumer data while simultaneously expanding product marketing through engaging content that contains information regarding the product so that it adds value for consumers to trust and choose the product.

The S-T (Strength-Threat) strategy is a strategy where a company utilizes its strengths to face or overcome threats. The strategy that can be used by IKM Rayhana Rezky Food is to utilize updated social media with advertising content that contains interesting information to counter more aggressive competitor promotions, and then maintain the quality of the marketed products and consumer interaction data to avoid cybercrime in digital marketing.

W-O (Weakness-Opportunity) strategy is a company's strategy to minimize its weaknesses by leveraging existing opportunities. The strategy that can be applied by IKM Rayhana Rezky Food is to expand the use of social media accounts with engaging content that easily goes viral, build product trust through strengthening consumer testimonials, and optimize product information to increase interaction and expand market share.

W-T (Weakness-Threat) strategy is a company strategy taken to minimize weaknesses and avoid threats. The strategy that can be pursued by IKM Rayhana Rezky Food is to expand the use of social media accounts to counter more effective promotions from competitors, and then optimize product information to build trust and prevent cybercrime in digital marketing.

CONCLUSION

Based on the research conducted on IKM Rayhana Rezky Food, with the problem formulation of how the Marketing Strategy for Cooked Fish Products of Duyung Based on Digital Marketing (Study on IKM Rayhana Rezky Food in Sinjai Regency). After determining the marketing strategy using the SWOT analysis method, it can be outlined as follows:

1. The marketing strategy for fish processing products based on digital marketing implemented by IKM Rayhana Rezky Food is carried out by applying the concept of digital marketing in its product marketing, such as utilizing social media platforms like Facebook, Instagram, and WhatsApp to expand product promotion, increase interaction with consumers, and enhance consumer trust in the product. Then the focus on the digital marketing indicators of accessibility,

- interactivity, and credibility has been done correctly. However, it still lacks attention to the indicators of entertainment, irritation, and informativeness.
2. After conducting the analysis, it can be seen on the SWOT diagram that IKM Rayhana Rezky Food is in the first quadrant, indicating that IKM Rayhana Rezky Food has opportunities and strengths. Therefore, in order to enhance marketing and sales, IKM Rayhana Rezky Food can choose a strategy that supports an aggressive growth policy, commonly referred to as a Growth Oriented Strategy, so that it can compete with competitors.
 3. The S-O (Strength-Opportunity) strategy is a strategy that utilizes all strengths to seize and maximize opportunities. The SO strategy that can be pursued by IKM Rayhana Rezky Food is to utilize the latest social media to increase interaction with consumers and expand market share, leverage product advertisement content that includes information about product legality that is engaging and easily goes viral, and utilize interaction data to strengthen consumer testimonials. This strategy aims to leverage social media to gather consumer data while also expanding product marketing through engaging content that includes product information, thereby adding value for consumers to trust and choose the product.

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